

TFTG: Time Fidelity Traffic Generation through P4/Tofino Programmable Hardware

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Abstract—Ensuring bounded end-to-end latency and high reliability is essential for time-critical services, motivating the development of TSN and DetNet protocols to guarantee predictable and reliable network performance. Testing the performance of IEEE and IETF standards can be challenging due to the cost of commercial devices supporting their implementation. In this work, we present TFTG, a traffic generator based on Tofino capable of creating TSN and DetNet traffic with nanoscale precision and high throughput. The proposed solution can be used in different scenarios to test standards for synchronization, reliability, and scheduling, with high flexibility in its applications. With these functionalities, TFTG serves as an open-source solution that users can employ to test target device capabilities, abstracting different topologies and scenarios for multiple protocols and testbed configurations.

Index Terms—TSN, DetNet, Traffic Generation, P4

I. INTRODUCTION

SERVICES in scope of 5G/6G rely on end-to-end capabilities to deliver ultra-reliable and low-latency communications (URLLC). Some extended reality (XR) services expect communication reliability of almost 100% and a latency below one millisecond (ms) [1] similar to Industry 4.0 real-time requirements [2], calling for deterministic and reliable communications. In this context, IEEE Time-Sensitive Network (TSN) and IETF Deterministic Networking (DetNet) have emerged as promising networking standards to enable these deterministic, reliable, and low-latency communications. Despite similar goals and characteristics, TSN and DetNet operate at different network layers, with TSN confined to Layer 2 (i.e. Ethernet) and DetNet to Layer 3 (i.e. IP) [3]. Furthermore, TSN and DetNet can work together, with DetNet extending the TSN data and control plane into Layer 3, expanding and complementing its capabilities [4].

Based on these TSN and DetNet capabilities, many efforts emerged to implement their standards and functionalities. Although successfully implementing features like [5] and [6], these works face a fundamental hurdle: efficiently testing their solutions. This hurdle comes mainly from the following two challenges: **(I) the difficulty in accessing robust experimental environments** (e.g., those consisting of multiple network devices and applications), and **(II) the challenge of**

reproducing workloads compatible with TSN and DetNet applications (e.g., ensuring deterministic nanosec latency).

The first challenge (I) stems from budget constraints. Many researchers cannot afford the specialized hardware needed for comprehensive experiments with multiple network devices and real applications, leading to a reliance on simulations that may not fully capture real-world complexities. The second challenge (II) is accurately reproducing advanced TSN and DetNet scenarios. This requires not just generating traffic but ensuring deterministic, nanosecond-level latency, high throughput, and TSN/DetNet functionalities (e.g., FRER, ATS). Moreover, conducting controlled experiments across diverse devices under strict performance conditions—while replicating key TSN/DetNet factors (e.g., jitter, out-of-order delivery, packet loss)—adds further complexity.

FPGA- and DPDK-based traffic generators achieve nanosecond accuracy but have limited customization and total capacity. Commercial hardware solutions are costly and may still fall short for TSN/DetNet experimentation in 6G research. More recently, P4-programmable Tofino hardware has combined nanosecond accuracy with Tbps capacity [7], [8], [9]. However, it remains inflexible, lacking TSN/DetNet support and the ability to replicate key factors like jitter, packet reordering, and targeted losses.

In this work, we present TFTG (Time Fidelity Traffic Generator), an open-source architecture for high-performance, deterministic network testing in ultra-reliable, low-latency networks. Leveraging a P4 Tofino switch, TFTG generates up to 1 Tbps of traffic with nanosecond-level deterministic latency. It offers high flexibility, abstracting complex networks with multiple applications and devices on a single physical unit. Supporting TSN/DetNet protocols and functionalities, TFTG accurately replicates critical scenarios, addressing challenges (I) and (II) through a cost-efficient, high-precision experimental tool for TSN/DetNet.

Figure 1 shows how TFTG can abstract network topologies. In this example, the network operator has a Device Under Test (DUT) being used to connect an Industrial Control System (ICS) to the Field Devices of an industrial process. The operator aims to assess the DUT's performance, scalability, and reliability by simulating traffic from multiple devices. TFTG abstracts this traffic into a single physical device, delivering it accurately to the DUT for testing. In summary, the main contributions of this paper are:

- The design of a mechanism for high-performance deterministic traffic generation in TSN and DetNet networks;

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Figure 1. TFTG abstraction example featuring DetNet/TSN traffic from multiple endpoints to interfaces a DUT, streamlining performance, scalability, and reliability evaluation for high-fidelity physical environments.

- A P4 prototype implementation for the Tofino hardware with open-source artifacts for reproducibility;¹
- An experimental evaluation showcasing TFTG’s performance, accuracy, and scalability.
- A discussion about the research challenges and future directions in deterministic traffic generation.

II. RELATED WORK

To develop a flexible testbed for evaluating TSN functionalities, the authors of [10] proposed the EnGINE framework using commercial off-the-shelf (COTS) hardware and employing the Ansible framework for experiment orchestration. The versatility of EnGINE allows its application across different topologies and traffic types, providing a comprehensive tool to evaluate TSN functionalities such as time synchronization and traffic scheduling. Similarly, in [5], they implemented some TSN standards in a hardware testbed named TSN-FlexTest. They evaluate the impact of combining the Precision Time Protocol (PTP) for clock synchronization and Time-Aware Shaping (TAS) for traffic scheduling by replicating TSN traffic using *tcpreplay* while generating high-load cross-traffic with the *MoonGen* traffic generator [11]. This approach allowed them to observe how TSN can handle heavy traffic in a controlled testbed environment. In a work more focused on DetNet, Choi et al. [6] implemented a DetNet packet forwarding engine based on FPGA, capable of operating at 100 Gbps and guaranteeing a bounded latency of $6.25\mu\text{s}$ per node. However, the work does not specify how the traffic was created or the use cases in which their solution can be applied.

Different tools have been proposed to generate traffic for these and other TSN/DetNet implementations. In [12], an FPGA-based traffic generator for Ethernet packets was introduced, designed for high-throughput network evaluation. The FPGA board features a 10GbE interface and supports the generation of high-speed traffic but lacks flexibility in terms of generating arbitrary traffic patterns. Further developments in traffic generation were made with the P4-TG tool, introduced in [8], which is based on the Tofino switch architecture

and capable of sending Ethernet/IP packets at rates up to 1Tbps. However, P4-TG does not support the generation of arbitrary traffic patterns. A more flexible Tofino-based solution is presented by PIPO-TG [13], which allows the user to define different packet headers and traffic patterns, making it more adaptable for TSN applications. In [7], the authors further demonstrate the precision of PIPO-TG and its suitability for TSN experiments, specifically in high-precision timing scenarios.

Despite advancements, traffic generation for TSN and DetNet still faces major limitations. Socket-based generators like *iperf*, used in the EnGINE framework [10], fail to saturate high-bandwidth links [5]. FPGA- and DPDK-based solutions, such as TRex and MoonGen, struggle with scalability and throughput, limiting large-scale experiments. No existing solution combines TSN/DetNet’s strict requirements (nanosecond latency, determinism, precision) with advanced features (ATS, TAS, FRER) or accurately replicates key conditions like packet disorder, delays, and losses.

III. GENERATING TIME FIDELITY WORKLOADS

This section describes TFTG’s design principles, architecture, and workflow. Since TFTG is built on the Tofino switch, the design must be carefully optimized to align with Tofino’s hardware architecture, maximizing resource use and performance. Additionally, as TFTG aims to provide high-performance, precise, and flexible traffic generation, the architecture and implementation have been guided by the following design principles:

I High-performance and accurate blocks. TFTG’s blocks should deliver high-performance (in terms of throughput) and accurate packets (in terms of deterministic inter-packet gap times). To achieve this, TFTG blocks must avoid operations such as drops and recirculations, in addition to preventing packets from passing through unnecessary blocks, which increases the number of processing latency.

II High abstraction capacity. TFTG components should offer a high level of abstraction, enabling the generation of traffic patterns that mirror a wide range of applications

¹Available in: <https://github.com/intrig-unicamp/TFTG.git>

and scenarios. To accomplish this, TFTG must support various protocols, TSN, and DetNet functionalities and facilitate the creation of multiple concurrent streams.

III Usability. TFTG should be easy and practical to use, allowing network tests to be configured in just a few steps. To ensure this, TFTG must include preprocessing blocks that streamline test generation, simplifying both configuration and execution.

IV Low resource overhead. TFTG should minimize resource usage during testing, allowing resources to be shared with real traffic passing through the switch. Additionally, by reducing the resources needed to reproduce a flow, TFTG can support more concurrent flows, boosting its overall scalability.

Based on these principles, Figure 2 presents TFTG's architecture and workflow. In the figure, all of TFTG's components are shown in blue. Blocks with solid lines must always be processed, while blocks with dashed lines are optional, depending on the specific use case and user settings. The figure also highlights the blocks responsible for implementing some of the TFTG functionalities and use cases (e.g., PREOF, TAS, ATS, etc.), which are discussed in Section IV.

User block. The user block serves as TFTG's interface, allowing users to define the traffic patterns to be generated. This interface, implemented via a Python script, enables users to specify applications, TSN and DetNet functionalities, and network flows, configuring parameters such as throughput and inter-packet times.

Preprocessing block. The preprocessing block processes the information from the user block, generates all the necessary configuration files (such as P4 code, table entries, and port settings), and initiates the switch setup, preparing it to begin traffic generation.

Processing block. The processing block handles packets and flows according to the defined policies. It processes two types of packets: template packets generated by the Tofino traffic generation unit and normal packets received from external devices. Template packets are modified to represent the user-defined applications and flows. All incoming packets pass through the traffic classification subblock, which distinguishes between normal and template packets, routing them to the appropriate subblocks for further processing. At this stage, the TFTG processing checks whether a packet is scheduled for that specific moment (scheduling block). If so, the packet is edited accordingly (packet editor); otherwise, it is dropped. Once edited, scheduled packets are sent to the forwarding and replication block, where the necessary flow policies are applied. Finally, the packet is routed based on queue and priority decisions. Next, the packet may go through size correction, multicasting, or pipeline switching units in the traffic manager, depending on the user-defined policies. In the egress pipeline, a measurement block can be activated to extract relevant traffic statistics before the packet is sent out if configured by the user.

With these blocks clearly defined, the TFTG workflow unfolds as follows (see Figure 1): (1) the user specifies the traffic settings to be injected into the network; (2) the preprocessing block generates the necessary configuration files and initiates

the switch execution; and (3) the processing block receives and handles the generated packets, applying the required actions to reproduce the desired traffic accurately.

A. Design challenges

As TFTG is specifically designed for the Tofino switch, there are some limitations of the Tofino architecture that impact its design.

Restricted to headers. The P4/Tofino switch lacks the capability to modify packet payloads. Moreover, its internal traffic generation unit restricts payload flexibility, as it can only generate payloads of a specified size without allowing modification on a per-packet basis. Consequently, packets generated by TFTG contain random payloads that do not reflect specific application data. Our approach, therefore, focuses solely on header manipulation.

Recirculation dependency. Although TFTG minimizes recirculations to enhance scalability, recirculations are essential for introducing deterministic latency. This need arises because the Tofino pipeline cannot "hold" a packet while processing, meaning each packet must be immediately sent out, dropped, or recirculated. When a packet enters the pipeline before its designated send time, we rely on recirculation to defer its transmission. However, this approach can introduce unintended latency if the recirculation duration exceeds the remaining wait time before the packet's scheduled send.

IV. TRAFFIC GENERATION USE CASES

In this section, we present some scenarios where TFTG can be employed to test different devices within a TSN/DetNet network. These use cases extend beyond conventional flow generation (e.g., simulating applications or endpoints) by integrating traffic generation with TSN/DetNet functionalities and events that affect latency-sensitive networks, such as packet reordering or delay distributions over a wide range. This demonstrates TFTG's unique ability to abstract complex scenarios that are not supported by any other solution in the market or literature.

1) Packet generation for time-sensitive applications.

Packet transmission and forwarding in deterministic networks must be executed with high temporal precision, as even minor timing deviations can significantly degrade real-time application performance. One use case our solution addresses is the transmission of DetNet/TSN packets with nanoscale precision. This capability enables our solution to serve as a precise packet source for any application while also providing a robust tool to assess the packet-handling capacity of a chosen DUT.

2) TSN Packet transmission with TAS control.

TSN introduces several standards aimed at achieving bounded latency, taking into account flow requirements such as deadlines and packet size. Among these standards, the Time-Aware Shaping regulates when each flow can be forwarded based on its priority and pre-established time cycles. Each forwarding port configures a Gate Control List (GCL) with the time each queue is open and closed to send packets. Besides, the device must be aware of

Figure 2. TFTG Architecture and Workflow.

the bigger packet length a queue must receive to add a Guard Band (GB) where no packet can be sent to prevent it from being finished out of its time slot. Our solution implements TSN traffic to be transmitted through multiple ports implementing TAS, defining the number of queues, cyclic time, the bigger packet length for each queue, and the GCL for each port. This use-case can be used to evaluate the performance of a TAS configuration in a real environment, abstracting the real topology.

- 3) **TSN Packet transmission with ATS control.** An alternative scheduling approach offered by TSN is the Asynchronous Traffic Shaper (ATS), which, unlike TAS, is unaffected by clock desynchronization among network devices. In ATS, packets are initially classified based on priority and assigned to FIFO-shaped queues associated with each transmitter. Subsequently, packets from queues of the same priority are aggregated into shared queues, which are managed by an algorithm such as the Length Rate Quotient (LRQ). LRQ regulates transmission by considering the ratio between the frame size and the link rate of each queue. Finally, frames are transmitted from the shared queues according to strict priority. In this use case, our solution emulates ATS behaviour using LRQ as the shaping algorithm. To achieve this, we configure the relevant ports and priorities for incoming packets and define the transmission rates for each priority level.
- 4) **Packet Duplication using FRER and PREOF.** Aiming to increase reliability, IEEE and IETF develop Frame Replication and Elimination (FRER) and Packet Replication, Elimination, and Ordering Functions (PREOF). Both techniques are based on nodes sending duplicate messages through preconfigured paths. These messages contain a sequence number, making the device capable of recognizing duplicated packets and avoiding forward duplicates. In this use case, our solution is configured to act as a node that realizes the duplication of the packets

according to one of those techniques. Therefore, we can test whether a network node can correctly recognize and drop duplicated packets.

- 5) **Testing reordering function.** Besides duplication and elimination, another crucial function in the FRER and PREOF techniques is reordering packets at some nodes. The sequence number in the headers also indicates the packet order, allowing a node to reorder the incoming packets if configured so. We also present another use case for our solution: sending unordered packets to test whether the DUT can properly make the reordering function.
- 6) **gPTP Synchronization mode.** To reach determinism, we need to ensure precise time synchronization across network devices. While DetNet leaves this synchronization to the lower layers, TSN applies the generic Precision Time Protocol (gPTP) through a spanning tree. The synchronization can be divided into two phases, one to calculate the link latency between the nodes and the other to make the synchronization. The link latency calculation is periodic and is realized by the nodes that will be synchronized by exchanging a few messages with the nodes that will synchronize them. The synchronization phase starts with a master node sending synchronization messages that pass through all the nodes to be synchronized until all nodes are synchronized. Our solution is configured to act like a node in those gPTP domains and is responsible for synchronizing other nodes. It receives messages from the nodes requesting to be synchronized, confirms the request, and sends the messages to the link latency calculation. It also sends the synchronization messages of the gPTP protocol, where we configure the periodicity of the synchronization messages. Acting like a master node or like an intermediary node, called a bridge node in the protocol, it adds a value to the correction field of the protocol. This way, TFTG can be used to test if the

Figure 3. Experimental evaluation results of TFTG for different scenarios.

devices are gPTP capable and also test their limitations regarding the periodicity with which they can receive the synchronization messages.

V. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

In order to assess the performance, accuracy, and scalability of our solution, we performed different experiments seeking to evaluate the main aspects of the delivered traffic. As evaluating every aspect of all use cases individually is not feasible, our evaluation focuses on the following objectives:

- (i) **Accuracy Assessment.** We evaluate the TFTG’s accuracy by examining the accuracy and determinism of the generated latency. The objective is to compare the intended latency with the actual latency produced by our solution.
- (ii) **Performance Analysis.** We explore the maximum performance of TFTG, focusing on throughput and how a loss of accuracy in the latencies can impact the final throughput.
- (iii) **Scalability Evaluation.** We analyze the ability to scale by assessing the number of flows/applications that TFTG can generate and how this can impact TFTG’s performance and accuracy.

Setup. We implemented a prototype of TFTG on the commercial programmable Tofino 1 switch using the P4 network programming language. In our experiment, we connected the

Tofino switch to an external server via 10 Gbps links and used the switch to run TFTG, replicating TSN and DetNet traffic with high fidelity. The server is only used to receive packets generated by TFTG and measure latency/throughput. Note that throughout the discussion of results, “latency” refers specifically to one-way latency and is measured using Tofino’s egress timestamp, which marks the moment a packet passes through the egress pipeline. This represents the transmission time rather than the actual arrival time at the DUT, as additional factors such as link propagation delay and DUT processing time (e.g., NIC and OS overhead) influence when the packet is ultimately received.

A. Accuracy

To assess accuracy, we conducted two experiments. The first experiment evaluated the desired latency to test our solution’s response to a range of latency from hundreds of nanoseconds to one millisecond. In this setup, TFTG generated 10,000 packets, with the latency starting at 100 ns for the first packet and increasing by 100 ns per packet, reaching 1 ms by packet 10,000. The second experiment replicated a real-world trace (*cross 900Mbps 10pps*) from a TSN topology, as measured and published by the Deterministic6G project [14]. The objective is to assess TFTG’s performance across a broad range of latencies and evaluate its accuracy in reproducing latency traces from a real network topology.

Figure 3(a) presents the first experiment's results, which measured latency from 100 ns to 1 ms. As shown, TFTG exhibits a slight loss in accuracy (approximately 200 to 400 ns) between the desired and actual latency, particularly when the desired latency are below 1000 ns. However, this difference becomes almost imperceptible as the desired latency increases, effectively becoming negligible for latency in the range of hundreds of thousands of nanoseconds. This minor discrepancy arises because TFTG occasionally requires packet recirculations to ensure the actual latency meets or slightly exceeds the target latency to maintain deterministic latency generation. When a packet is near the desired latency threshold but requires an additional recirculation, this process, which takes about 200 to 400 ns, introduces a small loss of precision.

To demonstrate the impact of this on real trace reproduction, Figure 3(b) shows the latency replication results for one trace from the Deterministic6G project [14]. Despite a small difference between the target and reproduced latency, TFTG accurately replicates the behavior of the real traces, keeping the accuracy difference within a maximum of 400 ns.

B. Performance

For our performance evaluation, we conducted an experiment to assess whether the throughput aligns with the desired configurations, such as inter-packet latency, packet sizes, and number of simultaneous connections. Additionally, we evaluated whether the generated traffic could achieve the server's line rate of 10 Gbps.

To achieve this, we generated 1, 5, and 10 simultaneous connections, varying packet sizes between small (64B), medium (512B), and large (1500B). The latency for these connections was set at 10,000 ns, reflecting the average latency observed in real topologies from the Deterministic6G dataset. Additionally, this latency is suitable as it only exceeds our 10Gb physical link's capacity in the most demanding test case (10 connections with 1500B packets).

Figure 3(c) presents the results for the test cases designed to evaluate how precision loss between expected and generated latency impacts the final throughput of the generated traffic. Since Tofino lacks a native mechanism to log outgoing traffic throughput, we calculate the throughput based on the inter-packet gap of packets received at the server, the number of active connections, and packet size. In the figure, gray bars represent ideal throughput (assuming perfect accuracy), while green bars indicate actual delivered throughput.

As shown, the difference between desired and actual throughput is minimal with small packets. This occurs because smaller packets require shorter recirculation times, leading to lower latency precision loss and, thus, a throughput closer to the expected rate. Conversely, with larger packets, the recirculation process takes longer, which increases precision loss in latency and reduces throughput accordingly.

Additionally, the number of active simultaneous connections impacts accuracy and throughput. As more connections are active, the different recirculating flows must share resources, increasing recirculation times and negatively affecting accuracy and throughput. This issue also impacts the solution's scalability, which will be discussed further below.

C. Scalability

Our scalability evaluation assesses the impact of multiple simultaneous flows, each with varying packet sizes, on the latency accuracy generated by TFTG. This approach replicates a realistic scenario with multiple applications running concurrently (e.g., similar to the topology abstracted in Figure 1) to evaluate TFTG's fidelity in reproducing such conditions. To this end, we replicated the settings from the previous experiment, configuring the target latency to 10,000 ns. Figure 3(d) compares the intended versus measured latency across different numbers of connections and packet sizes.

Results indicate that while smaller packets experience minimal precision loss, even as the number of simultaneous connections increases, larger packets – or “heavy flows” – exhibit a significant precision drop, with up to a 50 percent increase in latency compared to the target. This degradation is particularly evident in scenarios with numerous concurrent connections, highlighting the challenges of maintaining deterministic generation under heavy flow conditions. However, dealing with heavy flows is a known challenge in networking, commonly addressed in the literature due to its broad implications across similar contexts [15].

D. Limitations and discussion

Our analysis demonstrates TFTG's effectiveness in generating latency with high fidelity across varying packet sizes and connection densities. However, certain limitations impact its precision, particularly under heavy flows and high concurrent traffic conditions. Specifically, our accuracy assessment reveals that while small packets can achieve near-target latency values, larger packets introduce a measurable discrepancy, especially when multiple flows contend for resources. Since large packets (e.g., 1500B) are uncommon in most TSN applications, this limitation is unlikely to affect the reproduction of real-world experiments or scenarios. However, the requirement for packet recirculation to meet latency targets often adds 200–400 ns to each packet's latency, leading to an unavoidable precision loss. This impact on latency accuracy is accentuated when heavy flows are present, as seen in the scalability evaluation, where latency discrepancies can reach up to 50 percent above the intended latency.

Additionally, while TFTG's performance analysis confirms it can approximate high-throughput conditions, throughput is diminished when generating traffic with large packet sizes or managing a high number of concurrent connections. The recirculation needed for latency precision reduces achievable throughput, particularly for flows with large packets. As TFTG relies on the hardware's recirculation process, it inherently faces resource constraints when scaling up the number of connections, affecting both latency accuracy and throughput. This limitation is not unique to TFTG; similar issues are reported in the literature, highlighting an ongoing challenge in precise latency generation for heavy and concurrent traffic scenarios.

Finally, while TFTG proves scalable up to a point, the system's ability to accurately represent real-world traffic patterns diminishes under extreme conditions. Nevertheless, TFTG

surpasses state-of-the-art strategies in its ability to generate scenarios with complex network abstractions, supporting a greater number of connections and protocols. This capability makes TFTG a valuable tool for experimental research and testing in advanced 5G and 6G network environments.

VI. RESEARCH CHALLENGES AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

Stateful communication. Although other works, such as P4R [9], have shown the potential to establish stateful connections for testing network devices, their focus remains on stateful protocols like TCP without support for TSN or DetNet functionalities. As a result, no existing network tester can fully simulate the behavior of state-dependent applications or appropriately respond to the outputs of these applications. Additionally, even for stateless connections, such as UDP, current traffic generation solutions struggle with complex applications, managing only simpler cases like our gPTP synchronization. Moreover, none of these testers can replicate real application payloads, focusing solely on Layer 2 and 4 protocols.

Programmable hardware limitations. Despite the advantages of programmable network devices, they still face limitations due to constrained resources and computational capabilities, which restrict both memory access and processing power. For example, programmable switches lack arithmetic operations, rely on basic comparisons, and have a limited number of processing stages. While SmartNICs offer more flexibility, they compromise on performance and precision. As a result, network testing solutions must balance these trade-offs, often employing techniques like recirculation and fixed-point representations of real numbers. However, these methods can reduce the accuracy and performance of the solutions, preventing them from reaching the line-rate performance of the devices.

Multi-layer application-specific traffic generation. A significant challenge in achieving time fidelity traffic generation is accurately representing traffic patterns and behaviors specific to diverse applications, particularly those beyond traditional networking protocols. While current solutions focus on generating traffic up to Layer 4, advanced network testing requires traffic patterns that mirror the behavior of application-layer protocols (Layer 7) and cross-layer interactions. For instance, in 5G/6G and Industrial IoT networks, applications often have unique timing and sequence requirements that affect the performance of TSN and DetNet functionalities at lower layers. Achieving high fidelity for these scenarios will require traffic generators capable of emulating complex, multi-layer interactions and dynamic application behaviors that can adapt based on feedback from the network. This challenge calls for further exploration into hierarchical and application-aware traffic generation models, as well as programmable hardware support for cross-layer protocol processing, to enable precise, application-specific network testing.

VII. CONCLUDING REMARKS

This article introduces TFTG, a traffic generator with innovative features for deterministic communications. By leveraging Tofino programmable hardware, TFTG delivers a powerful

tool, capable of producing traffic with nanoscale precision and supporting high throughput, making it an ideal tool for testing TSN and DetNet protocols in various network scenarios. Its flexibility enables users to abstract complex network topologies and simulate traffic from multiple devices. It provides a valuable open-source solution for researchers and network operators seeking to assess device capabilities and network performance. TFTG addresses key challenges in deterministic traffic generation and provides a flexible, scalable solution for testing the capabilities of devices and protocols in next-generation networks.

While TFTG demonstrates impressive performance, it still faces challenges related to the recirculation and payload flexibility limitations inherent in the Tofino switch. While small packets exhibit minimal precision loss, larger packets, and high-traffic scenarios introduce measurable latency, particularly as the number of simultaneous connections increases.

Despite the challenge, TFTG offers significant improvements over existing solutions, demonstrating its potential to support complex network abstractions and a high number of concurrent flows. Further work includes refining its accuracy and throughput under extreme conditions.

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